

Figures of Speech In The Poetry Of Divine love for Al – Hallaj (309 Hijri)

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Abstract

He is Al-Husayn ibn Mansur al-Hallaj, and he is called Abu Mughith, and it was said: Abu Abdullah (1), a philosopher, is sometimes considered among the great devotees and ascetics, and sometimes in the group of atheists. It is originally from the white of Persia, and it was raised in Iraq or (Better), and moved to Basra, Hajj, and entered Baghdad and returned to Tester. His command appeared in the year 299 AH, and some people followed his method of monotheism and faith. Then he used to travel around the countries and spread his method secretly, and they said: He used to eat little and pray a lot and fast forever, and that he was showing the Shiite doctrine of the Abbasid kings, and the doctrine of Sufism to the common people, and in the multiplication of that, he claimed the presence of the divine in him.

Introduction

The people differed about Hallaj (3), one part exaggerated its veneration, one that exaggerated its expiation, and another part stopped it (4), in addition to this, the Sufi sheikhs also differed (5), most of them singled out him and denied that he had a foot in Sufism (6).

IbnHajar al-Asqalani (d. 852 AH) stated in his book entitled “Lisan al-Mizan” that Sheikh IbnArabi (d.638 AH) used to venerate Hallaj (7), and Judge Yusef al-Nabhani (d. 1350 AH) considered him among the saints and mentioned to him dignities several (8). In contrast, there are those who denounced Hallaj, such as Al-Tanukhi (d.384 AH). As he mentioned that he used to show miracles and tricks, such as miracles and tempt ignorant people (9). As for Hallaj's poetry, it was imprinted with the character of rationality and direct expression of psychological meanings - philosophical and emotional - in a style related to meanings without words, and with sent sentences (10), in addition to that, the poet used the graphic image because of the power of expression and accuracy of the depiction. On divine love and longing for the ideal; He says: (From the fast).

He applies, and what he knows, and his secrets apply like a sparkling bright flash

As the speed of an illusion for those whose delusion is on the thinness of the jealous mysterious (11).

And from that he said: (from simple)

And the best of love is what we talk about, like fire does not bring any benefit while it is in the stone (12)

And his saying: (From Mukhlaa Al-Basit)

Oh sun ohBadrOh dayYou are heaven and hell (13)

As for the words of Al-Hallaj, he was filled with Sufi expressions, so he used the phrase:

The whole, the whole, the whole, the exchange, the parts and the whole, the sentence, the condition and the conditions, as well as the philosophical and mystical terms, from the method (nowhere), the place and the essence, the remembrance, ghosts, temples, witness, witnesses ... and the conjunction of annihilation, ancient relic, fall, disbelief, faith, quality, theology, humanity and light And its personalities, affection, existence, existence, connection, communication and communication ... (14).

From the promises at the beginning, it seems that Al-Hallaj's poetry presents meanings that can be divided into sensual and cultural meanings, where the sensual poetry of Al-Hallaj presents the affairs of his material life, as opposed to the poetry of Al-Hallaj, as he presents many intellectual topics that were protest and proof of his philosophical, verbal and mystical views (15).

It is noted that the poet's image is one of the important pillars in building his poetic text. It helped him show the sensual side to support the meaning that would be formed and visualized in the sensual representation (16).

However, the poet's poetic text comes primarily from the soul, and expresses its desires, emotions and audiences of imagination, and moves the topic from its general objectivity to the topic of the topic, the feelings, feelings, emotions, visions and ideas that this soul suffers from. It did not come as a poetic witness in the context of the text, but rather came in harmony with all its harmonious components that wanted to be in this way of expression, in order to reinforce what the text wanted in its entirety (17).

Hair beauty is derived from the beauty of the image. Because the image is the mainstay of poetry and its texture, and it is the beginning of the thread that leads us to poetic construction, and the extent of poetry depends on creativity in photography (18). Therefore, we will stop here at the concept of image as a crucial term, without going into detail.

The second source: Image is a crucial term:

There have been many studies dealing with the poetic image. It is difficult to enumerate them, and despite this multiplicity and disparity, this opinion reflects the totality of issues related to the critic's ability, awareness and purpose, and if the old concept limits the image to simile and metaphor, the hadith expands the concept in its frame, so the rhetorical image is no longer the only image intended by the term ; Instead, the image - in the new sense - may be devoid of metaphor in the first place, and here there are real terms used, but it forms an image that denotes a fertile imagination (19).By adopting photography, poetry colors its images with all kinds of tangible things, and it becomes visual, auditory, tangible, taste and olfactory images, and it is far from abstracts, comfortable in metaphor, metaphor, representation and metaphor, and all kinds of metaphors, and it tends to move, vitality and diversity, you can convey to us the poet's emotion; But it may also convey to us the idea that drives it, and the image that the poet's imagination creates is nothing but a means of using language in a way that ensures that his feelings (emotions and thoughts) are conveyed to us in an effective manner, and since the image always depends on sensory expressions, it was closer to our perception (20).Of course, when we want to study the artistic characteristics of any literary work, we must begin to study its images. Because the image is one of the most important means of aesthetic formation for the poet, if not the most important (21), it is what liberates the poetic energy latent in the world, and which prose keeps captive to him (22).Thus, it is in its simplest meaning a drawing based on words, so the description, simile and metaphor can leave an image, or the image can be presented to us in a phrase or sentence that is dominated by pure description. As something more than an elaborate reflection of external truth reached our imagination, every poetic image of that is to some extent metaphorical (23).

In fact, the poetic image "is nothing but an embodiment of abstract ideas, psychological thoughts, and natural scenes, whether sensual or imaginary" (24) and the image that affects the recipient or the reader, is the image stemming from emotion, and hence the imagination, it is the researcher on the organic unity of the poetic text. Because imagination is the ability by means of which a certain image or a single feeling can dominate several images, or feelings in the poetic text, thus achieving unity among them in a manner similar to melting (25).

The term imagination refers to the ability to form mental images of things that are absent from the reach of the senses, and the effectiveness of this ability is not limited to the mere automatic restoration of perceptual perceptions related to a specific time or place. Rather, its effectiveness extends far beyond that (26).The unity that controls the work of the imagination means the complete harmony between the heart and the mind, between the sincere observation and the imagined faculty, between the tangible and the imperceptible, and this indicates that the imagination is not just a perception of things absent from the sensation, but rather a complex event with many elements, adding experiences New (27).Not surprisingly, the picture is usually used to denote all his wealth related to the sensual expression, and it may be fired at times; It is synonymous with metaphorical use (28).

This, and the role of the image in the process of perception, as it differs from one mind to another, appears. Thinking is associated with the image, and the image may take the form of an idea; As it is its first article (29) and from that, the picture is a strongly charged speech, usually consisting of physical elements, lines, colors, movement, shadows, which in its multiplication carry an idea or emotion, that is, it suggests more than the apparent meaning, and more than the reflection of the external reality, and in the aggregate they form a harmonious whole(30).

The mixing of meaning, words and imagination, all of which is called the image, and from its interconnectedness, compatibility and looking at it once when critiquing the text, the literary assessment (31) is based here.As for the role of the image in poetic creativity, it remains the form of feeling for the creator, and it is saturated with his sentiment and emotion. It indicates the poet's skill, and foretells his artistic abilities, when he makes the indications he seeks visible to the recipient (32).

Not to mention, the poetic image is a body that extends from one word to another, it is not an analogy and is not a symbol of something alien to it. But it symbolizes itself, it is an end, it is the idea, it is knowledge, it is the dream (33).The image is associated with realistic experience, but the imagination does not deviate from reality except to tell reality through its reproduction. Imagination helps to form the external reality in a new form in the literary work (34). There is no doubt that the image in poetry is the artistic form that words and phrases take after being organized by the poet in a purely graphic context. To express one aspect of the complete poetic experience in the poetic text, using the energies and potentials of language, in connotation, composition, rhythm, truth, metaphor, synonymy, contrast, contrast, homogeneity, and other means of artistic expression (35). The graphic arts came from (metaphor, metaphor and metaphor), one of the most important elements contributing to the construction of the poetic image for Hallaj. As the image in his poetry was derived, by means of graphic

methods in organizing his poetic experiences, through which he was able to expand his perception as a force charged with interpretation (36).

The graphic image is the expression of the intended meaning by means of metaphor, metaphor, metonymy, or embodiment of meanings (37). The graphic representation is the one that expresses, in an imagined sensible image, the mental meaning, the psychological state, the sensible event, the visible scene, the human model and the human nature, and then elevates the image that he paints to give it a short life, or a renewed movement (38). It is important to say that the poet Al Hallaj used the methods of statement in his poetic texts. To be a better expression of his feelings and his imagination, the poet looks at these various images, with a contemplative look and mobilizes himself, and expresses that in poetry. Therefore, we will deal with the graphic image in the poetry of divine love for the parlor to demonstrate the poet's capabilities and capabilities in poetic photography.

The first style: an allegorical image:

Metaphor in language: a metaphor: (borrowing) the thing from him: he was asked to loan it to him (39). Metaphor as an idiom: The metaphor is the first thing that mankind knew in the sciences of statement It is the clarification of a matter that the addressee does not know by mentioning something else known to him to measure it against. And by development it came only in the structures of similar speech, and this is called metaphor. Metaphor is more lucid than metaphor and more informative than metaphor. The metaphor is the use of the word in a manner other than what it has been developed for, due to the similar relationship between the meaning conveyed from it and the meaning used in it, with an implication deviating from the original meaning (40).

The metaphor is a linguistic metaphor for its similar relationship between the real and the figurative meaning (41). Metaphor plays an important role in constructing the poetic text, as metaphor is the form in which attributes and names are given to things that cannot be compatible with them in reality (42). The metaphor has great importance, as it takes precedence over "in the form of human speech, as it is a major factor in motivation and stimulation, an expressive tool, a source of synonymy and a multiplicity of meaning, an outlet for emotions and intense emotional feelings, and a means of filling gaps in terminology" (43).

The metaphor is from the graphic methods based on the relationship of likeness, but it is different from the simile by omitting one of the parties For a rhetorical purpose aimed at the writer or poet, it is divided into two types: declarative metaphor and metaphor (44). And from the extrapolation of the poetry of the divine love of the poet, we found it to have used the metaphor of both types: the declarative one in eighteen positions, and the noun in sixteen positions (45). An example of his metaphors is his borrowing (gear) used in war to protect from arrows and other things, to submit to the beloved, as he borrows the word (sword) being the most powerful means in war, for crying between the hands of the beloved. This crying is the beneficial means of approaching the beloved and obtaining his approval. As the poet lived with love and love, he is his spiritual strength, his heart nourishment, he is the fiery of his desires, the creator of his glories, the absolute of his melodies, and he is his vast, glittering horizon, in which the lights shine, and in which the secrets are revealed (46); He says: (From convergent)

So take from your left the gear of submission, and tighten the right with the sword of the Baka (47)

He also borrows the term (ambush), which is used to entrap the enemy, to denote slippage in the path of love, and the arrival of estrangement by the beloved of the lover, in his saying: (from the convergent)

And yourself, be afraid, on the alert, of the Alfa ambush (48)

For the poet, love is Sufism, and Sufism is love, for Sufism in its essence is a constant, vigilant and vivid connection with God, is an experimental attempt to return man, in every part of his spiritual being, to his Creator and Master (49).

And we find that he borrows the word (coming) to desertion, and the word (darkness) to denote the bad situation that the lover feels in a state of abandonment, as he borrows the term (torches of light), to denote the commitment of obedience in walking the path of love, which achieves a state of inner serenity for the lover to God Almighty, by saying:

(From convergent)

If desertion comes to you in darkness, interpret in the torches of the light of Safa (50)

Thus, the Hallaj proceeds, borrowing the term (fire), to denote what longing creates an inner heat in the heart of the lover, saying: (From the simple)

Likewise the facts are the fire of longing that is burning from the truth if they are no longer and if they refuse (51)

This is what indicates that the Creator and the creature in separation is a master and a slave, and in fact is a single entity united by love, as a fixed quality in both parties. The poet concludes these praises by stating that the fire of longing heals its truth, which is represented in the continuous communication between the Creator and the creature in all cases, from the outside, inward, inward and in fear (52).

Elsewhere, the poet borrows the words (hearing) and (sight) and parts of the body, to signify the perfection of love and the heartfelt attachment to the beloved, from his saying: (from the simple).

Oh all of me, my hearing and my sight, the entirety of my whole, my followers, and my parts

O all of me and all of all are confused and all of you are clothed with me (53).

This divine love of the poet led him to the realization of the divine unity, in which a person is not able to achieve himself with it, except through this divine longing, this feeling and this love, and he abandons his selflessness, the source of darkness, nothingness, ignorance and torment (54).

However, the poet's metaphorical image is not a luxury, or artistic affection, but an image emanating from a psychological impulse whose path is driven by a sincere emotional emotion, which gives it a sensual connotation, and at that time the latter is a connecting part of his poetic intent, and the result of the relationship between his motive of saying and his sincere emotional emotion (55). And from that, the poet was able to borrow the term (the sun) to denote the beloved and its rising at night, and its enlightenment and its staying without sunset, to signify the arrival of love to the point of perfection, so there was no remaining in the heart of the lover, another lover, and the metaphor of the term sun here, to denote the beloved who does not disappear. Mentioning it about his heart, with the borrowing of the word (flight), to denote that the heart is directed towards the beloved, with a longing for it He says: (From the light).

The sun rises if I love at night and is enlightened, so it has no sunset

The sun of the day sets at night and the sun of hearts does not set

He who loved the beloved flew to him longing to meet the beloved (56)

And in the same figurative style, he says: (From the simple creator)

And my heart flew with the feathers of longing in a boat in the winds of Azmi (57)

The passion of love, which is one of the ancient attributes of God in the opinion of al-Hallaj, worked in his heart until it overcame him, and became a constant characteristic of him. And as the principle of love dictates that the unity between the loving is necessary, you became evident to me, O my God, and I realized that you were aware of love, validating my doctrine in the unity of witnesses, and I became certain that it was you who appeared to me and filled my heart. That is why the poet borrows the term (eye) to the heart to denote the vision of the beloved in the heart, for it was manifesting you in a small part of my body, called the heart).

I saw my Lord with the eye of my heart, so I said: You have no doubt, you (58).

From the term (Al-Rasha) the beloved poet is depicted in a beautiful way, saying: (From the sand).

Breeze of the wind Say to the sprinkle: The rose did not increase my thirst (59).

The poet borrowed the term (bribe) to denote the beloved, as if he were saying:

)Wind anise, tell the sprinkler), and perhaps he was trying to heal this rift, and since every wind does not move trees and does not release a trace, it is a breeze (60). Therefore, the breeze from the wind does not please its blowing, and it is easy breathing (61).

From the symbolic poetry, the poet stands at the word (the sea), using this graphic means, to denote the path of walking and behavior in Sufism, saying: (From the fast).

I am still floating in the seas of passion, the waves lift me up and fall down (62).

He also said in an allegorical graphic image: (From the simple).

If I utter the whole sunnah in you, and if I hear, then I all hear in you (63).

The theology remains invisible, for it is in the absolute, and man is in the threshold of the limit. As for the human nature, which is the secret of the light of the Godhead, according to al-Hallaj, it is revealed to those who have put forward the sense and the mind, and are attracted by true love. As if in his exposure, this veil pierced the world of creation, so it seemed to create a human appearance, for love is the only path to true knowledge (64).

And from that the poet portrayed (the place), which belongs to the people of perfection, who dominated the conditions by means of mastery. The place is higher than the maqam, which is a stage in Sufi behavior; Because settlement is a state in the heart, (and it is) an upbringing of the heart in the light of the unseen without change, lest any change occur to the one who holds the standing. The origin of the place is the witnesses of the truth in the mystery of the heart in the adjective of the transfiguration in all cases, and the poet resorted to depiction by metaphor, by borrowing the place between the skin and the bones and a beloved process in this place, to signify the perfection of love for the beloved, saying: (From long).

And my soul placed you between my skin and my greatness, so how do you see me if I lose you, I will do (65)

This divine love reaches for the parlor to unify himself with the truth, so that knowledge is achieved in man, so that man in turn, through this love, realizes this true existence transcending the concept of the limited place, and this is how the feeling of the parlor blends with his divine love, which made him a whole and whole love. And if this love does not stop at a limit. He borrowed the image of the moon joining the influence of the sun to signify the perfection of love for the beloved, which is right in Sufi idiom. It is the annihilation of the servant's existence in the same truth, the Almighty, just as the erasure is the annihilation of his actions in the act of truth, and the obliteration is the annihilation of the attributes of the truth (66), his saying: (From the fast)

The two forms joined in a state and became a successor in the injustice of the world (67)

From the sensual graphic images, which were characterized by their mystical, abstract, symbolic character, borrowing the term (light), to denote the beauty of the beloved; He says: (It is simple).

The light of your face is a secret when I witness it, this is generosity, charity and generosity (68)

In the same context of metaphorical graphic images, Hallaj depicts his beloved, through the metaphor of the word (Riyadh), which contains every beauty, to depict the beloved's beauty, he says: (From the uprooted)

YamenRiad has its meanings - it has contained all art (69)

Among the declarative metaphors of the poet, he said: (From the abundant)

Not to inform my loved ones that I rode into the sea and the ship broke (70)

The second type: the simile image:

Linguistically, simile: representation (71).

It denotes the sharing of one thing with another in a meaning, so the first thing is the analogy, and the second is the analogy with it, and that meaning is the face of the simile, and there must be a metaphor, its purpose, and the analogy (72). In the terminology of the scholars of the statement: it is the indication of the participation of two things in a description of the thing in itself (73), or in other words a similar contract between two or more matters intended to share them in an attribute or more, using an analogy, for the purpose of which the speaker intends (74) The meaning of this is the metaphor, a statement that a thing or things shared one or more attributes with others, and an analogy and similar to it are used for that, and they are the two sides of the analogy, and the other two are the two sides of the analogy. It should be noted that the metaphor is one of the major rhetoric sections praised by critics in the past and present, because of its great impact on constructing the literary image and drawing a wonderful artistic painting that affects human emotions and feelings. It gives it glory and majesty to style, gives it wit, novelty and innovation, and renders it strength, pleasure, movement and activity (76). Hence, most poets used metaphor in their poems and styles because of its artistic value, and what allows them to act in saying, so they took care of it and varied in their uses of it. And they made it a tool with which to express their souls and feelings, just as they portrayed ideas with it and removed them with it from their abstraction (77). Based on this perception, the poets were warmly greeted by the metaphor. In their view, it is a sign of talent, the manifestation of ingenuity and the means of virility and superiority in the field of poetry. Poetics has been linked in the depiction of many poets, with the ability to create that image (78). When searching in the pages of Hallaj's office, we find that he has used the method of simile in sixteen places (79). However, the poet, in forming his metaphorical image, tends to use the tool of simile (al-kaf), and he used it in nine places (80). It is likening Al-Kaf to portray his love for his beloved with his love for his soul, in order to indicate to the recipient the extent of the poet's love for emotional participation, and his skill in choosing literary methods that have strong influence on emotions and conscience, by saying: (From the eradicated one).

And you are with me as my soul, and in it I love (81)

And in his depiction of lovers while they are in a state of annihilation from themselves; He likens them to the Companions of the Cave, who did not know when they woke up how long they stayed, and it is clear that what is meant here is death, not the emotional, and love here is expressed by Sufis (with the traits), as it pervades the slave with the attributes of truth, so that the truth permeates it and is not void of what appears to it Some of his attributes, so the servant is the mirror of truth (82), hence the metaphor (al-kaf), which is used in what the rhetoricians see As the similarity between the two sides becomes stronger until they are about to be one thing, in his saying: (from the simple)

You see the lovers of a death in their homes, like the cavemen, and they do not know how long they stayed (83) Elsewhere, the poet likens the love of his beloved to his love for the beloved. He says: (From the scattered sand)

For I am you, as you are my forgetful and my purpose (84)

And Hallaj said, using an analogy, to depict the movement of his secrets at their speed, with the hint of lightning and the speed of illusion, saying: (From the fast)

He applies and does not know, and his secrets apply as the glow of a bright light

As the speed of illusion of those whose delusion is upon the mysterious and sunken flour (85)

Truth created hearts, placed its secret within them, created breaths and made its course inside the heart between it and the mystery, and placed knowledge in the heart and monotheism in secret, so no soul ever emerged except with the sign of monotheism and the significance of knowledge on the carpet of turmoil in the world of deism, and every soul is devoid of this. He is dead and his owner is responsible for him. The Hallaj perished from everything, turned away from everything, and his love for his Lord consumed him, making him feel that this love filled his existence, heart and soul. He loves every atom of his body, and with all the energy of his soul, until his whole being is considered nothing but love and a manifestation of his master and his beloved (86), and here he does not conceal his love.

And the best of love is what we have talked about, like fire that does not bring any benefit while it is in stone (87)

It is now he and the beloved one. The lights were revealed to him, and with this revelation his horizons expanded, and there is no time in it and no place surrounding it ... As the phenomena in the true sense are similar, just as the meme (with) and its eyes are similar in their opening up and down, that is, in their launch to the unlimited, and then in (Unite them) as (unite) top and bottom or maximum and minimum.

And (by the union of) the meme and the eye, the dual consciousness vanishes to remain the monogamous unit. With this vanishing, true knowledge is achieved (88), and in this regards Al-Hallaj, likening the case of his attachment to his lover, to the amber when mixed with the hernia:

(From sand)

You have made your soul in my soul, as amber raises the fruity musk (89)

There is no doubt that the metaphor has a great effect on expressing meanings, conveying ideas, and entertaining souls with images and imaginations, bringing words closer to minds, and elevating them from the ground to the space of imagination, and the more a person progresses in this height, the farther his depiction is in the heart, and more firmly established in The soul (90). He also has: (From Al-Raml)

Your spirit mixed in my soul just as wine mixes with albumin water (91)

The poet did not limit himself in his similes to the use of the simile tool (Al-Kaf). Rather, the letter of the simile (as if) was used in five places (92), but this tool is more eloquent than sufficient in denoting the attachment of the likeness to the likeness, in terms of the strength of similarity and symmetry (93).

An example of these similes is his analogy to himself in love with the drowning in the sea, from which only the tips of his fingertips appeared. To seek relief and escape from drowning, saying: (from the simple)

As if I was drowning, his fingers appear to be drowning in a sea of water (94)

He likens himself to the distant one, and he calls the absent loved one always, from his saying: (From the long one)

Suffice it with sadness that I always call you as if I were away or as if you were absent (95)

In this pictorial aspect of the analogy al-Mursal (96) with the instrument (as if), what the hallaj said is similar to himself, while on the journey and the Sufi behavior of the rider riding in the sea, and the waves of the sea turn him sometimes upward and sometimes downward, saying: (from the simple)

As if I'm between waves turning me back and forth between ascending and descending (97)

And in the same context, he says: (From the long)

I have encapsulated all of you, my Holy One, reveal me, even as though you are in myself (98)

We find the poet using an analogy (for example), in his analogy with someone who acquainted him with a secret, and he did not keep it by himself, the lover among people, and his mind has gone in saying: (from the simple)

Whoever teaches him a secret and sleeps with it is like me among the people who have been distracted (99)

In his simile, the poet does not stop at using the metaphor of the sender, in the aforementioned graphic images. Rather, we find him using the eloquent metaphor (100), when he addresses his beloved that he is an eye for the eye and a heart for the heart. He says: (From the uprooted)

You are for the eye, and you are for the heart (101).

The third type: the meta-image:

Metonymy as a language: a source of a metonymy, or an alias. And I was about such-and-such, if I left the declaration of it. The metonymy is derived from the metonymy, and thus the metonymy is included in the metonymy (102). The metaphor is to express a certain thing with an unrelated expression for the sake of the thumb.

Such as saying: "a metaphor for" meaning (103).

A metaphor, according to the scholars of the statement: is to express something, whether a word or a meaning, with an expression that is not explicit to signify it, for a purpose, such as the thumb on the listener (104). Idiomatically: it is a term by which it is wanted other than the meaning that it was assigned to, with the permissibility of wanting the original meaning, because there is no presumption preventing his will. The metaphor contradicts the metaphor in all its parts of metaphor and metaphor (105).

If a metaphor is a term used and intended, its meaning is necessary, although it is permissible to want that meaning (106).

A visitor to the poet's office finds that he used the metonymy style in the poetry of divine love in a lesser proportion than its predecessors: the allegorical image and the metaphorical image, and it came in only three places (107). One of its examples is that he meant death about the condition of lovers, when they were abandoned by their lover, after their connection, as an expression of the end of pain and hardship, in addition to that, he meant to resurrect the connection of the beloved to them after that, an expression of the happiness and pleasure that they find when this connection, in his saying: (From simple)

People, if they deserted after they arrived, they died, and if they arrived again, they sent (108)

He also meant the king of his beloved in his heart about the perfection of his love for him, saying: (from the uprooted)

You possessed my heart, and I understood in every valley (109)

He meant by saying: (They are people of mystery and for the secrets were created), on the authority of the divine divine, and that people were created to know it, from his saying: (from the simple)

They are the people of a secret, and for the secrets they were created, they do not bear patience for those who were forbidden (110)

After this review of the poet's graphic means, we found that it was more than the use of metaphor, and perhaps what motivated him to do that was the nature of the subject in which he was organized, which was the expression of his love for the divine self without the attributes of man, so he found in the metaphor the best way. To communicate what he wants to others. Al-Hallaj was able to beautifully harness the allegorical graphic, its meanings and ideas, linking the physical and spiritual aspects. In contrast, the poet used another important method of graphic representation, which is simile, and he had a fundamental role in communicating what he wanted to the recipient, as well as used the metonymy method a little, and he had a role in highlighting what is in himself to others.

References

- IbnHajar Al-Asqalani (d. 852 AH): Lisan Al-Mizan, Study, Investigation and Commentary by Adel Ahmed Abdel Mawgid, and Ali Muhammad Muawad, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al Fikr, no I, 1414 AH / 1993 CE.
- IbnKatheer (d. 774 AH): The Beginning and the End, edited by Ali Shiri, Beirut - Lebanon: House of Revival of Arab Heritage, 1st ed. 1408 AH / 1988 AD.
- Ibn al-Malqin (d. 804 AH): Tabaqat al-Awliya, edited by Mustafa Abd al-Qadir Atta, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar al-Kutub al-Ilmiyya, 1st ed.
- Ibn Al-Nadim (d. 380 A.H.): Al-Fihrist, edited by Ibrahim Ramadan, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al-Marifa, 2nd Edition, 1417AH / 1997AD.
- Abu Al-Adous, d. Yousef: The Metaphor in Modern Literary Criticism, The Cognitive and Aesthetic Dimensions, Amman - Jordan: The National Press, 1st Edition, 1997 AD.
- Abu al-Fida (d. 732 AH): The History of Abi al-Fida, the abbreviated name in the news of mankind, commented on it and put his annotations on it by Mahmoud Dioub, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyya, 1st Edition, 1417AH / 1997AD.
- The hero, Dr. Ali: The image in Arabic poetry until the end of the second century AH, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al-Andalus, 1st Edition, 1980 AD.
- Al-Tanukhi (d. 384 AH): Nashwar Lecture and Consultation News, edited by Mustafa Hussein Abdel-Hadi, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyya, 1st Edition, 1421 AH / 2004 AD.
- Al-Tunji, Dr. Muhammad: The Detailed Lexicon of Literature, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al-Kotob Al-Ilmiyyah, 2nd Edition / 1999 AD.
- Al-Thaalabi, Abu Mansour (d.429 AH): Philology and the Secret of Arabic, Cairo - Egypt: Al-Istiqama Press, no. I, d. T .
- Al-Jarim, Ali, and Amin, Mustafa: The Clear Rhetoric, Beirut - Lebanon: The Cultural Books Foundation, 1st Edition, 1429 AH / 2008 AD.
- Al Jarbi, Dr. Muhammad Ramadan: Applied Rhetoric, Al-Fateh University - Libya: from ELGA publications, no. I, d. T.
- Al-Jarjani, Sharif Ali Bin Muhammad (d.816 AH): Book of Definitions, Beirut - Lebanon: House of Revival of Arab Heritage, 1st Edition, 2003 AD.
- Hallaj, Abu al-Mughith al-Husayn:
Explanation of the HallajDiwan, edited by Kamel Mustafa Al-Shaibi, Beirut - Lebanon: Al-Jamal Publications, 2nd Edition, 2007 AD.
- Al-Tawasin, prepared by RadwanAs-Sah, presented by Abdel-Qader Al-Hosni, Syria - Damascus: Dar Al-Farqad, 1st Edition, 2010 AD.
- Al-Hamdani, Dr. FarisYassin Muhammad: The graphic image in the poetry of Ibn Al-Dhahir Al-Arbili (d. 677 AH), Baghdad - Iraq: Al-Rafidain Literature Magazine, Issue (69) for the year 1435 AH / 2014 CE.
- Al-Khatib Al-Baghdadi (d. 463 AH): History of Baghdad or the City of Peace, Beirut - Lebanon: The Arab Book House, no. I, d. T .
- Khader, Dr. Fawzi: The Elements of Artistic Creativity in IbnZaidoun's Poetry, Kuwait: Abdul Aziz Saud Al-Babtain Prize for Poetic Creativity Foundation, no. I, 2004 m.
- Al-Dulaimi, Dr. Samir Ali Samir: The Image in the Poetic Formation, Baghdad - Iraq: General Cultural Affairs House, 1st Edition, 1991 AD.
- De Louis, Cecil: The Poetic Picture, translated by Ahmed Nassif Al-Janabi, MalekMiri, and Salman Hassan Ibrahim, Baghdad - Iraq: Publications of the Ministry of Culture and Information, Al-Rasheed Publishing House, no. I, 1982AD.
- Richards: Principles of Literary Criticism, translated and presented by Dr. Mustafa Badawi, reviewed by Dr. Louis Awad, Cairo - Egypt: The Egyptian General Organization for Authorship, Translation, Printing and Publishing, no. I, 1963 m.
- Al-Zarkali, Khair El-Din: Al-Alam, Beirut - Lebanon: House of Knowledge for Millions, no. I, d. T.
- Sorour, TahaAbd al-Baqi: Al-Husaynibn Mansur al-Hallaj - martyr of Islamic mysticism, Cairo - Egypt: Hindawi Foundation for Education and Culture, no. I, 2014 m.

- Abdullah HasanJabbaret, al (2018), Chemical synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles induced biocompatibility for anticancer activity. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development*, 9 (11). pp, 352-357.
- Al-Sulami, Abu Abd al-Rahman: *Tabaqat al-Sufism*, edited by Mustafa Abdel-Qader Atta, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al-Kotob Al-Ulmiyyah, 1st Edition, 1419 AH / 1998 AD.
- Salloum, Dr. Daoud: *Literary Criticism*, Baghdad - Iraq: Al-Zahraa Press, no. I, 1967 AD.
- Al-Shaarani (d. 973 AH): *The major classes called Balwaqih al-Anwar in the classes of the good guys*, corrected and corrected by Abd al-Ghani Muhammad Ali al-Fassi, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar al-Kutub al-Ilmiyya, 1st Edition, 1418 AH / 1997 AD.
- Al-Safadi, Salah Al-Din Khalil (d.764 AH): *Al-Wafi of the deaths*, verified by Ahmed Al-Arnaout and Turki Mustafa, Beirut - Lebanon: House of Revival of Arab Heritage, 1st ed.
- Drum, Dr. Hassan: *The graphic image in the rhetorical tradition*, Mansoura - Egypt: The Faith Library, 1st Edition, 1426 AH / 2005 AD.
- Abd al-Rahman, Afif: *The Dictionary of the Abbasid Poets*, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Sader for Printing and Publishing, 1st Edition, 2000 AD.
- Assaf, Dr. Sassine: *The Poetic Image and Its Models in the Creativity of Abu Nawas*, Beirut - Lebanon: The University Foundation for Studies, Publishing and Distribution, 1st Edition, 1402 AH / 1982 AD.
- Ashmawy, Dr. Mohamed Zaki: *Studies in Contemporary Literary Criticism*, Alexandria - Egypt: The Andalusian House, no. I, 1988AD.
- Asfour, Dr. Jaber: *The Artistic Image in the Critical and Rhetorical Heritage*, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al-Tanweer for Printing and Publishing, 2nd Edition, 1983 AD.
- Afifi, Dr. Hamid Sadiq: *Applied Criticism and Budgets*, Cairo - Egypt: Al-Khanji Library, No. I, 1978 AD.
- Anuz, Dr. Sabah Abbas: *The artistic image between its sensuality and the rhythm of meaning*, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al-Salam Press, 1st Edition, 2010 AD.
- Awwad, Abdullah Ahmad Ayal: *The Artistic Picture in the Poetry of QaisIbn Al-Khatim*, Amman - Jordan: As-Safir Press, 1st Edition, 2016.
- Gharib, Rose: *An Introduction to Modern Criticism*, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al-Makhfouf, no. I, 1971 m.
- Al-Ghunaim, Dr. Ibrahim bin Abdul Rahman: *The Technical Image in Arabic Poetry is an Example and Criticism*, The Arab Company for Publishing and Distribution, 1st Edition, 1416 AH.
- Fadl, Salah: *Constructivism Theory in Literary Criticism*, Baghdad - Iraq: House of Cultural Affairs, no. I, 1987 m.
- Judge Nabhani (d. 1350 AH): *Karamat Al-Awliya Mosque*, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyya, 2nd ed. 1417 AH / 1996 AD.
- Al-Qatt, Abd al-Qadir: *The Affective Trend in Contemporary Arab Poetry*, Cairo - Egypt: The Youth Library, no. I, 1986 m.
- Qutb, Syed: *Artistic Photography in the Holy Quran*, Cairo - Egypt: Dar Al Shorouk, no. I, 1995 m.
- Kashani, Kamal al-Din (d. 735 AH): *Sufi conventions*, edited by Alois Springer, Calcutta - India: No printing press, no. I, 1845 m.
- Mustafa, Ibrahim, and others: *The Median Lexicon*, Beirut: House of Revival of Arab Heritage, 1st Edition, 1429 AH / 2008AD.
- Moroccan, Dr. Hafez: *Anxiety, Alienation, and Death in Al-Shabi's Poetry*, An Analytical Critical Study, Minya - Egypt: Abu Hilal House for Printing and Publishing, no. I, 1999 m.
- Makarem, Sami: *Al-Hallaj in Beyond Meaning, Line and Color*, Beirut - Lebanon: Riad Al-Rayyes for Books and Publishing, no. I, 2003 m.
- Jabbar, Abdullah Hasan, et al. "Nanocomposite Assisted Green Synthesis of Polyvinylpyrrolidone-Silver Nanocomposite Using Pandanusatrocarpus Extract for Antiuro lithiatic Activity." *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy* 11.6 (2020): 1436-1442.
- Al-Midani, Abu Al-Fadl (d. 518 A.H.): *Complex of Proverbs*, Cairo - Egypt: No printing press, no. I, 1352 e.
- Nassef, Dr. Mustafa: *The Literary Picture*, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al-Andalus, 2nd floor, 1981 AD.
- Nashaat, Kamal: *In Literary Criticism - Study and Application*, Baghdad - Iraq: Al-Mustansiriya University Publications, 2nd Edition, 1976 AD.
- Nassar, Nawwaf: *The Literary Dictionary*, Amman - Jordan: Ward House for Publishing and Distribution, 1st Edition, 2007 AD.
- Wahba, Majdi, and Al-Muhandis, Kamel: *Dictionary of Arabic Terms in Language and Literature*, Beirut - Lebanon: Lebanon Library, 2nd Edition, 1984 AD.
- Al-Yafei, Afif Al-Din (d. 768 AH): *Mirror of Jinan and the lesson of vigilance in knowing what are considered accidents of time*, Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyya, 1st Edition, 1417 AH / 1997AD.
- Die, Dr. Gaseous : *The Science of Manifestation Styles*, Beirut - Lebanon: The Lebanese House of Thought, 2nd Edition, 1983 AD.
- Literary Art - Races and Types*, Beirut - Lebanon: Modernity House, 4th Edition, 2008 AD.

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